

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Empowering the Serbian EMF RATEL System for Monitoring RF-EMF Through Drive Test

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ABSTRACT The Serbian EMF RATEL system has been monitoring radiofrequency (RF) electromagnetic fields (EMFs) since 2017. As one of five active European systems for continuous monitoring of RF-EMF, it has been able to provide insight into the long-term, temporal variability of the field, especially in areas with increased sensitivity to RF-EMF exposure. Although it has proven its benefits for the general public and the scientific community, the relatively small number of RF-EMF sensors installed at fixed locations reveals its weakness – the inability to cover larger urban areas and provide adequate information on the spatial distribution of the overall field. The distribution of sensors at scattered points is a consequence of the limited costs of system development, as well as the practical difficulties in obtaining an authorized permit to install sensors at a public or private location, which is crucial for the use of any large number of sensors. Consequently, the EMF RATEL network has been upgraded to perform spatial field analysis by integrating the functionality of the drive test, for the first time among existing monitoring systems, developing it to a higher level and achieving progress in RF-EMF research by establishing a single EMF entity for observing both temporal and spatial changes of RF-EMF in the territory of interest. This paper presents some technical details of the integration of the drive test into EMF RATEL, as well as preliminary quantitative results of the corresponding drive test measurements to validate the approach. The aim of this paper is to encourage other, similar EMF monitoring systems to further develop the topic of RF-EMF observation.

INDEX TERMS RF-EMF monitoring, exposure, wireless sensor network, temporal and spatial variability.

I. INTRODUCTION

The worldwide spread of numerous sources of electromagnetic fields (EMFs) is increasing the intensity of the field in the environment, while at the same time raising public concerns about the impact of EMF on their health [1].

Therefore, significant efforts have been made to measure and assess human exposure to EMF [2], especially in the radiofrequency (RF) range, by conducting large-scale cam-

paigns and studying RF-EMF exposure from a number of new telecommunication technologies [3], [4], [5], [6], in different environments [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], paying attention to both personal [12] and occupational exposure [13], [14], [15].

Appropriate methods have been developed, ranging from in situ measurements to mixed methodologies, with some improvements [16] and [17]. Moreover, several progressive approaches are emerging, such as measurements by drone [18], [19], [20], drive tests [21], [22], [23], and state-of-the-art EMF monitoring networks [24], five of which are active across Europe [25], [26], [27], [28], [29],

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with the Serbian EMF RATEL being the most recently enhanced [29].

The results obtained expand the knowledge about the presence of RF-EMF in the human environment, while helping scientists to analyze in more detail the risk assessment and appropriate communication with the population about EMF [30], [31], [32], in relation to different everyday scenarios. At the same time, these results and scientific outcomes may help the general public to establish a more rational perception of the inevitable presence of RF-EMF in their modern lives.

Recently, the drive test method has attracted attention for its ability to collect data on the spatial distribution of EMF in different environments – urban and suburban [21], [22], [23], demonstrating its value especially along routes of particular interest. Several research studies have been conducted to represent the existing field levels over large areas in cities [21], [22], [23], [33], as the most dynamic human environment.

Furthermore, the drive test methodology has been adopted by some national authorities [29], [34], to provide the public with confidence that field levels in accessible areas are within prescribed, safe reference levels, as applicable in national laws or international recommendations [35], [36], [37].

In addition to the safety aspect, drive test measurements are also starting to serve as the basis for numerous services, such as those for RF-EMF exposure prediction, based on machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) [38], [39], [40], EMF pollution mapping [41], [42], [43], [44], along with some commercial applications [45], as well as correlating field exposure with population and building density [46], and even more for combining spatial and temporal mapping, to facilitate rapid identification and assessment of RF-EMF exposure hotspots [47].

The drive test approach has proven to be a significant contribution to the topic of EMF research. Unfortunately, there is a gap in existing research, where many drive test results have been published in numerous scientific papers; however, they cannot be found integrated into any specific EMF entity and offered to the wider community.

Recognizing the advantages of this methodology, EMF RATEL has been enhanced with a drive test functionality, for the first time among EMF monitoring systems, establishing an important, unique EMF entity for analyzing both the temporal and spatial behavior of RF-EMF, offering its results through an Open Data framework [48] and [49].

This paper presents the technical details of the integration of the drive test into EMF RATEL, where Section II provides a brief overview of the organization of EMF RATEL, while Section III provides the main steps of the integration performed. Section IV presents the quantitative results of the conducted drive campaigns, while Section V discusses the results. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

II. SUMMARY OF THE EMF RATEL SYSTEM

The EMF RATEL network was established in 2017, thanks to the efforts and vision of the Serbian Regulatory Authority for

Electronic Communications and Postal Services (RATEL). It is based on autonomous RF-EMF sensors, which are distributed throughout the territory and connected in a wireless network, as conceptually shown in Fig. 1.

EMF RATEL covers larger cities in the Republic of Serbia, as illustrated in Fig. 2, with the number of EMF sensors in each city being correlated with the population density of the city (indicated by a blue circle and the corresponding number).

The system is growing year by year, with the installation of several new RF-EMF sensors, as shown in Fig. 3 (ending in May 2025), according to the annual development budget.

These RF-EMF sensors are associated with specific types of locations, based on RATEL's commitment to covering the most sensitive zones to RF-EMF exposure. Considering the location, 55% of the sensors are installed in schools and kindergartens, as shown in Fig. 4, while the distribution by city is shown in Fig. 5, where it can be observed that the capital city of Belgrade, as the most populous city in Serbia, with more than 2.5 million of permanent inhabitants, accordingly has the largest number of installed sensors.

EMF RATEL was originally designed to cover the territory of Serbia, as shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 6, using scattered sensors, with continuous monitoring of the electric field (E-field) at these locations, as shown in Fig. 7.

The system, like other monitoring systems [25], [26], [27], [28], was intended for the general public to present daily E-field variations in a simple way, allowing them to view any desired period in the past, as given in Fig. 7, so that the history of variations can be analyzed. According to a 2022 research study [11], the basic parameters of these systems for RF-EMF monitoring are shown in Table 1.

However, these networks continue to expand and by the end of September 2025 contain the following number of sensors: NOEF = 500, SRMF = 324, ODO = 249, ANCOM = 200 and EMF RATEL = 116. However, these numbers are expected to increase even further in the future.

As for EMF RATEL, this system has the smallest number of EMF sensors; however, by their dominant installation in schools/kindergartens, both RATEL and the Government of the Republic of Serbia demonstrate a valuable social responsibility regarding the safety of the youngest, in terms of practically unavoidable exposure to RF-EMF radiation.

A. OVERVIEW OF CONTINUOUS MONITORING

One of the earliest installed sensors in the system continuously collects data for 2744 days, while the others from 675 to 2744 days, where the histogram of the acquisition days in the monitoring process is given in Fig. 8. Moreover, the total number of results in the system database reached 48 million, with a distribution as shown in Fig. 9, ranging from 162000 to 658560 measurement samples. The number of measurements per sensor is given in Fig. 10, where the sensors are sorted from the earliest installed to the newest on the abscissa of the diagram.

FIGURE 1. EMF RATEL monitoring network concept [50].

FIGURE 3. Growth of EMF RATEL.

FIGURE 2. Coverage of the territory of Serbia by EMF RATEL [29].

FIGURE 4. Sensor's distribution per location.

FIGURE 5. Distribution of sensors per city.

Given such a large number of measurements, especially per sensor, the usual display of field level on the timeline, via the public part of the system portal, shown in Fig. 7, had to be limited to a period of 240 days. Consequently, many details in the behavior of the E-field remain hidden and thus some statistical methods have to be used to get a thorough insight into the levels, as shown in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12.

These two figures contain a basic statistical analysis of the monitored averaged E-field levels, by location type [50] and city, revealing similar behavior of field in almost all location types, during 2023, 2024 and 2025 (ending in May 2025), except in the case of public institutions where a slight increase in field intensity can be observed. The situation is very similar with the E-field in cities, without any drastic annual changes.

Moreover, in all cases, the averaged monitored field levels are well below the nationally prescribed reference levels [51], where 11 V/m is the lowest permitted E-field level.

Also, regarding the quartiles Q1 and Q3, as the values that divide the data set so that the lowest 25% of the data are below

a certain point – Q1, and 75% of the data lie below this point – Q3 [52], it can be observed that they are almost consistent across all types of locations and cities, except in the last two years for faculties, student dormitories and hospitals.

The changes in these locations are the result of empty faculties and dormitories in late 2024 and the first half of 2025, due to political protest by students in the Republic of Serbia, which led to the complete suspension of classes and the closure of these institutions. Moreover, these protests have been violent, on several occasions in some cities, requiring the intervention of medical teams and the treatment of the injured in hospitals. Consequently, the detected E-field levels around hospitals are increasing in almost all quantities.

As for all other locations, the summarized analysis of the conducted field monitoring highlights the fact that the field levels have stabilized, which is an important indicator for the public, especially considering the upcoming national

FIGURE 6. Home page of the EMF RATEL portal [29].

FIGURE 7. Dissemination of EMF RATEL monitoring results [29].

FIGURE 8. Histogram of acquisition days.

implementation of 5G NR1 technology, expected in 2026 [53], in accordance with the adopted regulation on minimum conditions for the issuance of individual licenses [54].

Finally, more numerical values for these summary statistics in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 are provided in Table 2 and Table 3.

B. INSIGHTS INTO ON-SITE RF-EMF MONITORING

Much deeper insight into the E-field behavior, especially for the micro-environment in the vicinity of RF-EMF sensor, can be obtained by using a specific methodology for analyzing RF-EMF time series, such as the recently presented approach of time-averaging [50], through which multi-scale analyses can be performed, as shown in Fig. 13 [50].

An overview of the E-field behavior throughout the week can reveal patterns and common changes, and moreover,

FIGURE 9. Histogram of obtained results.

FIGURE 10. Number of results per sensor.

TABLE 1. Comparison of basic parameters between systems [11].

No.	Network	Started	Number of sensors	Frequency range	Logging time
1.	NOEF [25]	2015	480	100 kHz - 7 GHz	6 min
2.	SMRF [26]	2005	324	100 kHz - 8 GHz	6 min
3.	ODO [27]	2020	161	80 MHz - 6 GHz	120 min
4.	ANCOM [28]	2016	153	100 kHz - 7 GHz	6 min
5.	EMF RATEL [29]	2017	98	100 kHz - 8 GHz	6 min

can provide yearly comparison to see the increase in field intensity, as done in Fig. 13 and its case study for the period 2018-2022, which can also be an important approach for the population given the expected implementation of 5G.

Different patterns can be observed for both weekdays and weekends, as well as different E-field levels during these two periods, along with specific slopes of the curve before and after noon, which reveals the behavior of the local community in using telecommunications services [50].

Furthermore, this type of field analysis can be beneficial for comparative assessment of RF-EMF across several locations, as was done in [55] and presented in Fig. 14, which shows differences in E-field behavior as a consequence of the current EMF conditions in the site micro-environment [55].

Many details can be observed, such as daily or short-term patterns in the field behavior, peaks, slopes, dynamics, variability, level distribution, etc., each of which may be of interest to a specific target group [55]. In addition to all these elements, their annual comparison is one of the main features of the time-averaging framework, which is not so easy to do with the statistical approach shown in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12.

Such a review can reveal periods of increased exposure to RF-EMF, suggesting whether the population should take

FIGURE 11. Statistic by type of E-field monitored location.

TABLE 2. Statistical analysis by location type.

Location type	Year	Min	Mean	Max	St.dev.	Median	Q1	Q3
		[V/m]						
Center for culture	2023	0.46	2.27	5.22	1.49	1.94	1.47	2.62
	2024	0.71	2.29	5.28	1.47	1.90	1.48	2.71
	2025	0.66	2.28	5.21	1.46	1.77	1.51	2.56
	2023	0.98	2.34	5.14	1.21	2.14	1.42	2.93
Public institution	2024	0.99	2.55	6.93	1.44	2.27	1.51	3.09
	2025	0.94	2.59	7.72	1.59	2.25	1.64	2.98
	2023	0.00	1.54	3.76	0.92	1.48	0.80	2.01
School	2024	0.04	1.63	3.88	0.88	1.45	0.93	1.99
	2025	0.04	1.64	3.87	0.89	1.46	1.04	2.08
	2023	0.93	2.02	3.61	0.92	1.85	1.45	2.43
Faculty	2024	0.94	2.16	4.08	1.14	1.92	1.12	3.03
	2025	0.91	1.94	4.29	1.06	1.79	1.06	2.29
	2023	1.81	2.83	4.34	1.11	2.23	2.11	3.68
Students dorm	2024	2.09	2.86	5.32	1.38	2.22	2.17	2.52
	2025	1.84	2.93	5.43	1.43	2.56	2.19	2.63
	2023	0.44	1.62	3.25	0.75	1.46	1.00	2.18
Kindergarten	2024	0.52	1.74	3.63	0.82	1.53	1.12	2.22
	2025	0.21	1.85	3.64	0.93	1.65	1.30	2.34
	2023	0.93	1.51	2.39	0.46	1.51	1.15	1.72
Hospital	2024	0.93	1.57	2.65	0.55	1.61	1.14	1.73
	2025	0.84	1.56	2.68	0.56	1.55	1.20	1.77
	2023	0.73	2.15	3.54	1.08	2.14	1.40	2.93
Other	2024	0.76	2.30	3.73	1.09	2.51	1.59	2.88
	2025	0.87	2.25	3.65	1.02	2.50	1.55	2.68

any precautions, while also suggesting when the most appropriate period is for any additional field measurements [55], if needed for any further investigation, such as detailed spectral analysis of the field content.

III. DRIVE TEST INTEGRATION INTO EMF RATEL

EMF RATEL and other monitoring networks [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], uses distributed RF-EMF sensors, installed at fixed locations. This is due to the real difficulties in finding accessible and suitable monitoring locations, given that zones of increased sensitivity to RF-EMF exposure must be covered, in accordance with the provisions of national Law for non-ionizing radiation [56], as well as the process of obtaining an authorized permit to install sensors in a public or private location.

Unfortunately, the process of obtaining an authorized permit is crucial for installing a large number of EMF sensors, with a limited budget for system development. Therefore, the EMF RATEL system has been enhanced by integrating drive test functionality, as shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 15, which allows for a less demanding field analysis process,

FIGURE 12. Statistic by cities with E-field monitoring.

TABLE 3. Statistical analysis by city.

City type	Year	Min	Mean	Max	St.dev.	Median	Q1	Q3
		[V/m]						
Beograd	2023	0.27	1.87	4.34	0.99	1.85	1.00	2.53
	2024	0.04	1.89	5.32	1.02	1.89	1.09	2.41
	2025	0.04	1.90	5.43	1.07	1.84	1.06	2.59
Niš	2023	0.77	1.73	3.22	0.87	1.62	1.08	2.20
	2024	0.79	1.64	3.03	0.78	1.42	1.10	2.06
	2025	0.95	1.63	2.47	0.48	1.56	1.32	1.83
Novi Sad	2023	0.64	1.29	1.94	0.47	1.34	0.99	1.56
	2024	0.74	1.28	2.09	0.46	1.22	1.06	1.37
	2025	0.70	1.19	1.93	0.44	1.17	0.88	1.32
Valjevo	2023	0.66	1.64	2.65	0.82	1.62	1.29	1.96
	2024	0.78	1.75	2.81	0.84	1.70	1.36	2.08
	2025	0.70	1.69	3.04	0.98	1.50	1.26	1.92
Novi Pazar	2023	0.93	2.13	3.22	1.00	2.19	1.55	2.78
	2024	0.94	2.29	3.21	1.07	2.51	1.68	3.11
	2025	0.91	2.24	3.25	1.00	2.40	1.80	2.83
Čačak	2023	1.42	1.76	2.18	0.39	1.69	1.56	1.94
	2024	1.35	1.62	1.86	0.26	1.64	1.50	1.75
	2025	1.41	1.67	1.94	0.27	1.66	1.54	1.80
Vranje	2023	2.27	3.44	4.30	1.05	3.76	3.02	4.03
	2024	2.47	3.42	3.90	0.82	3.88	3.18	3.89
	2025	2.56	3.46	3.96	0.78	3.87	3.22	3.92
Cities with (2) sensors	2023	0.44	1.78	3.61	0.98	1.48	1.08	2.74
	2024	0.52	2.04	4.08	1.04	1.70	1.42	2.86
	2025	0.21	2.15	4.29	1.15	1.76	1.40	3.16
Cities with (1) sensor	2023	0.46	1.92	5.22	1.12	1.71	1.09	2.40
	2024	0.71	2.07	6.93	1.30	1.75	1.17	2.66
	2025	0.66	2.07	7.72	1.35	1.81	1.26	2.42

especially measurements on routes of particular interest in the area.

Such integration establishes a single EMF entity for observing temporal and spatial fluctuations of RF-EMF, as a valuable comprehensive indicator of field behavior in the territory of interest, while enriching the set of information for the community about this specific element of the environment.

The following subsections will present several technical details of the integration of drive tests, from the database to the public and administrative part of the system portal.

A. DRIVE TEST DATABASE MODEL

A drive test is established on premise where its campaign is associated with a populated area, such as a city. This is done intentionally so that future campaigns can be conducted in the same area, allowing for comparison of the collected results to obtain annual changes in field levels.

Accordingly, the system database is expanded with the data model shown in Fig. 16, which covers all important aspects of drive test integration.

FIGURE 13. Averaging over time – per week – 2018-2022 [50].

FIGURE 14. Comparative EMF evaluation per monitored locations [55].

The populated area that is the subject of spatial observation is stored in the table `t_drive_cities`, where each entity can have multiple associated drive campaigns, which are stored in the table `t_drive_campaigns`. This will allow the implementation of several RF-EMF observation campaigns and the monitoring of annual changes in the E-field present.

For each campaign, some supporting data is stored, such as *i)* basic campaign data – in the `t_drive_campaigns_infotable`, *ii)* files with measurement results from the measuring device [57] – stored in the `t_drive_parsed_files` table, and *iii)* field measurements along the route, stored in the `t_drive_results`.

In addition, the campaign is also linked to *iv)* an exposure assessment module that estimates exposure at each measurement point along the route, according to the national prescribed reference field levels [51], stored in the `t_drive_exposure` table, as well as to *v)* a key open data module, via the table `t_drive_open_data`, as the intention is to make measurements publicly available via the national Open Data portal [49].

1) CAMPAIGN DETAILS

The drive test feature is established on broadband field measurements, observing the total E-field strength at the

FIGURE 15. Drive test feature in the EMF RATEL system [29].

FIGURE 16. Drive test database model.

FIGURE 17. Details of the drive test campaign.

measurement point, calculating the contribution of active field sources in the vicinity. Data about the measuring device, its measurement probe, and the frequency range covered by the probe are stored in **t_drive_campaigns_info** table, as shown in Fig. 17.

In addition, data about the start and end times of the survey, the number of measurement points on the survey route, as well as the measurement uncertainty that accompanies the process, are stored here as valuable information for campaigns.

The original measurement result files are stored in the table **t_drive_parsed_files** and processed using a special, purpose-designed data parser, while the measurement details are stored in a separate table – **t_drive_results**.

2) DRIVE TEST PARSER DETAILS

The results of the measuring device used in the drive test [57] are stored in the Google KML format [58], which is used to display geographic data in services such as Google Earth. A basic overview of this file format is shown in Fig. 18.

A dedicated data parser is designed and integrated as part of the information logistics of the system [59], where the parsing process is activated after uploading KML files via the administrative part of the EMF RATEL portal [29].

3) DETAILS OF THE DRIVE TEST RESULTS

The parser extracts relevant data and stores them in the table **t_drive_results**, from Fig. 19, where the following data are of primary importance: *i*) time and date of measurement; *ii*) measured E-field level, as well as *iii*) GPS coordinates and altitude at which the measurement was performed.

Finally, within the **t_drive_results** table, it is possible and enabled to publicly display any individual measurement point or not, as a useful feature in case of some unforeseen problems with the measurement or the measuring device itself.

4) EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT MODULE

Broadband measurements observe the total E-field strength, with all components present, i.e. those originating from constant reference signals and variable data traffic channels of

telecommunication services, provided by active field sources present in the vicinity.

This type of measurement reflects the state of the field at the moment of measurement and the observed levels can be highly dependent on the real-time load of network and its services.

Moreover, broadband measurements are unable to distinguish the spectral content of the field present and cannot assess exposure by frequency, as define in the standard EN 50413: 2020 [60] and its Serbian counterpart SRPS EN 50413:2020.

Therefore, the exposure assessment for this type of measurement, which is performed at each measurement point during the drive test, relies on the estimation of the lower and upper exposure boundaries of the overall exposure (Global Exposure Ratio – GER) [61], given by the following expressions:

$$GER_{\text{lower}} = \left(\frac{E_m}{E_{\text{ref max}}} \right)^2 \quad \text{and} \quad GER_{\text{upper}} = \left(\frac{E_m}{E_{\text{ref min}}} \right)^2, \quad (1)$$

where E_{refmin} and E_{refmax} are the prescribed reference limits for the frequency range of the measuring probe used [57], and E_m is the measured E-field value, obtained by broadband measurement.

These boundaries indicate in which range the actual exposure may be found [61], as shown in Fig. 20, where the upper boundary represent the worst-case of exposure and the lower boundary the best-case. Also, the maximum allowed exposure value is $GER_{\text{allowed}} = 1$.

The prescribed reference levels associated to the frequency range of the probe used are stored in the **t_drive_exposure** table, from Fig. 19, since broadband measurements are performed and therefore require minimum and maximum prescribed levels for a specific frequency range [51] and [61].

5) OPEN DATA MODULE

The national Open Data Portal [49] is the official place for publishing datasets from public institutions. Accordingly, the

```

Novi Sad 14112024.kml
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<kml xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
xmlns:xsd="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema">
  <Document>
    <name>MapEM 100kHz-6GHz</name>
    <Folder>
      <name>&lt;t;0.1</name>
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13:0:42</h5]]></description>
        <styleurl>&lt;t;0.1</styleurl>
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        </Point>
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13:39:30</h5]]></description>
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        <Point>
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        </Point>
      </Placemark>
    </Folder>
  </Document>

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FIGURE 18. KML file format for the drive test [58].

FIGURE 19. Details of the drive test measurement results.

EMF RATEL drive test offers its measurement data in three standardize file formats, JSON [62], XML [63] and CSV [64], as open standard formats for data exchange.

Measurement data are available in a machine-readable and open format, intended for reuse – for commercial or non-commercial purposes.

The link to the open data file for a specific drive campaign, used through the national Open Data Portal [49], is stored in the table **t_drive_open data**, as shown in Fig. 19.

B. DRIVE TEST ON THE PUBLIC SECTION OF THE SYSTEM PORTAL

The presentation of the drive test results in the public part of the EMF RATEL portal, shown in Fig. 6, is established in a simple and user-friendly manner, where the essential data are presented using the functions of Google maps technology, as shown in Fig. 15. The drive test route is displayed on the map, so that users can see in detail the environment in which the individual measurement was performed.

FIGURE 20. Exposure boundaries [61].

1) GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF FIELD LEVELS USING COLORS

For a more efficient and understandable presentation of the drive test results, a display of measurement points in appropriate colors, related to the field level along the route, has been implemented, as shown in Fig. 15 and Fig. 21.

The color palette is aligned with the recommendation of the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), given in the document ITU-T K.113 – “Generation of radiofrequency electromagnetic field level maps” (11/2015) [65].

The E-field levels that can be expected during the measurement are divided into eight groups, each of which is marked with a specific color, so that the user can get visual information about the measured field along the entire route.

2) DETAILS ABOUT THE DRIVE TEST CAMPAIGN

The publication of EMF RATEL drive tests is intended for the general public, who may not be well informed or educated about RF-EMF. Therefore, the publicly available campaign data are summarized in a minimalist form, as shown in Fig. 15 and Fig. 22.

Shown here is a reduced set of campaign information from the data model discussed in Fig. 17, representing basic details on campaign, along with the maximum and minimum measured E-field levels along the entire drive test route.

In addition, the maximum and minimum values of the upper exposure boundary only are given, as an indication of the worst-case exposure that the user may experience along the route. However, the exact position of minimal/maximal field levels, as well as upper exposure have to be found on the map.

3) DETAILS OF E-FIELD MEASUREMENT IN A SINGLE POINT

Each measurement point on the drive route can be selected to check details, such as broadband measured field levels and exposure boundaries, as shown in Fig. 15 and 23.

This practical feature of the system portal is valuable in relation to the personal concerns of individuals who may reside or pass near the measurement point. Here they can see the total E-field level, regardless of the location of the field source and the technology used for RF-EMF radiation, as well

FIGURE 21. Color-coded drive test route display.

FIGURE 22. Campaign details.

FIGURE 23. Details of individual measurement points.

as the exposure limits, bearing in mind that the maximum permissible exposure value is $GER_{allowed} = 1$.

C. DRIVE TEST ON THE ADMINISTRATIVE SECTION OF THE SYSTEM PORTAL

The administrative section of the system portal for drive test is established on the data model discussed in subsection III-A and has restricted access, only for authorized personal.

This part of the EMF RATEL portal manages details related to drive test campaigns, only some of which will be presented in the following subsections.

1) CITIES AND CAMPAIGNS ADMINISTRATION

According to the database model in Fig. 16, populated areas – cities, where EMF RATEL drive test campaigns are being conducted or will be conducted, are managed as shown in Fig. 24.

There is an overview of cities, showing the number of campaigns conducted in a particular city, as well as some related actions, such as deleting or editing a city, and a detailed overview of all campaigns associated with the city, as shown in Fig. 25.

In the campaigns section, a summary is provided with data about each campaign, regarding the date/time when the campaign measurement started/ended, along with initial statistics regarding their measurement results.

Moreover, new campaigns can be added in this section, while existing ones can be further processed with some of the actions, such as deleting, editing, or viewing measurement results.

After creating new campaigns and uploading the corresponding KML files obtained from the measuring device [57], relevant basic statistics are calculated and linked to the campaign.

Finally, it is envisaged that each campaign may or may not be displayed in the public part of the system portal, as shown in Fig. 15.

2) AUTOMATIC CALCULATION OF PRESCRIBED REFERENCE LEVELS

Exposure assessment is performed at each measuring point along the drive test route and relies on prescribed reference levels [51], which are used to calculate exposure boundaries [61], discussed in subsection III-A.4.

Regarding the frequency range of the measuring probe used [57], there is an automatic routine for calculating the corresponding reference levels, as shown in Fig. 26.

By entering the starting/ending frequencies of the range that is covered by the measuring device, reference levels are calculated and stored in the `t_drive_exposure` table for use.

3) OVERVIEW OF CAMPAIGN MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Each campaign is carefully reviewed before being published in the public section of the system portal. This review applies to both the route and the measurements, as shown in Fig. 27.

The drive campaign routes are displayed via Google maps, using the color palette recommended by ITU-T K.113 [65], as explained in subsection III-B.1, for a better visual experience of the measured E-field levels along the route.

Regarding acquired measurements, the data can be viewed via Google maps or via a table, as shown in Fig. 27, where each measurement point can be checked.

4) EDITING MEASUREMENT POINT DATA

In some cases, there is a need to edit data for a specific measurement point, such as an expected situation with a discrepancy between the GPS coordinates obtained from the measuring device and the actual situation on Google Maps.

These changes can be made in the administrative section, as shown in Fig. 27 and Fig. 28.

Regarding potential problems during the measurement task, it is possible to make each measurement point visible in the public section of the system portal or not.

FIGURE 24. Administration of drive test cities.

FIGURE 25. Administration of drive test campaigns associated to a specific city.

FIGURE 26. Automatic calculation of reference levels for exposure assessment in broadband E-field measurements.

D. DATABASE SCALABILITY

EMF RATEL’s information logistics is designed for a web application, in a PHP environment and is deployed on a Linux server and a MySQL database server.

The logistic is hosted on an internal RATEL server, which allows full control over the hardware and daily monitoring of the system performance. The system is currently allocated with a capacity of 100 GB for data storage, with the possibility of expansion as needed.

Moreover, the system database is designed for a maximum of 1000 sensors, which perform continuous monitoring of the E-field, along with 1000 drive test campaigns, where annual campaigns will be conducted for a specific city.

The entire information logistics is designed for 100 simultaneous accesses, while the Linux server can provide further web connections as needed.

Finally, regarding scalability, the system capacities can be expanded to a certain extent, especially in terms of storage, by adding an additional hard disc to the RATEL web server, and in that way expanding a number of sensors and drive test

campaigns, which can be processed in the future, while the web server can provide additional simultaneous accesses.

IV. QUANTITATIVE RESULTS OF DRIVE CAMPAIGNS

The EMF RATEL drive test service was launched in late of 2024 and currently has six completed campaigns, in some of the larger cities in Serbia. These campaigns are available via the system portal, as shown in Fig. 15 [29].

The following subsections will explain the details of how the campaigns were implemented.

A. DRIVE TEST PROTOCOL FOR EMF RATEL

The drive test protocol was prepared in accordance with the ITU-T K.113 recommendations in Section 6.1 [65], taking into account good practice in the telecommunication sector, where it is regularly used to assess coverage and other related parameters of a telecommunications network.

However, two adaptations of these recommendations have been made specifically for EMF RATEL and details on them will be explained in following subsections.

FIGURE 27. Overview of campaigns and corresponding measurement results.

FIGURE 28. Editing measurement point data.

1. Install the measuring device on a vehicle.
2. Set up Global Positioning System (GPS) equipment.
3. Set a drive test route.
4. Set the measurement time to 1 s.
5. Start driving (the maximum speed of 50 km/h).
6. Periodical stop the vehicle to perform additional measurements with handheld device.
7. When drive test is complete, take the measurements results and compare them with nationally prescribed reference levels.
8. If the measurement is above the reference level, indicate the specific point for further investigation.

FIGURE 29. Step-by-step driving test protocol.

1) PROTOCOL IN STEPS

The steps of the drive test protocol used in EMF RATEL are briefly shown in Fig. 29.

a: INSTALL THE MEASURING DEVICE ON A VEHICLE

E-field measurements are performed using a special purpose vehicle from RATEL, with a measuring device installed on the roof [57], as shown in Fig. 30.

FIGURE 30. Drive test vehicle with main measuring device [57].

b: SET UP GLOBAL POSITIONING SYSTEM (GPS) EQUIPMENT

The measuring device [57] is equipped with internal Global Positioning System (GPS) equipment to enable geographical positioning of the measurements.

c: SET A DRIVE TEST ROUTE

The route in EMF RATEL is usually predefined for certain cities, taking into account their areas of interest where there is an increased population density or they are frequently visited.

d: SET THE MEASUREMENT TIME TO 1 S

According to the ITU-T K.113 recommendations from Section 6.1, the measuring device is set with a measurement time of 1 s, “given that most common GPS devices provide position information every second” [65].

e: START DRIVING (THE MAXIMUM SPEED OF 50 KM/H)

The first deviation from the ITU-T K.113 recommendations is the driving vehicle speed, which is set to remain within the 10 m limit between adjacent samples, as suggested

TABLE 4. Brief details of the measuring devices used.

	Drive test measuring device [57]	Reference level measuring device [66]
Frequency range	100 kHz – 8 GHz	100 kHz – 6 GHz
Sensor type	Isotropic	Isotropic
Sensitivity	0.02 V/m	0.02 V/m
Dynamic range	52 dB	70 dB

for non-urban areas (speed around 36 km/h) and the measurement time 1 s [65]. However, the maximum speed is kept below 50 km/h.

This was a forced, practical change of the recommendations for urban areas due to two main factors *i*) the anticipated road conditions during rush hour in cities, taking into account the experience in [21], [22], and [23] and *ii*) low-speed vehicles require a special permit from the traffic police and the mandatory engagement of a police escort in these cases, which will consequently slow down the process of taking the driving test.

Consequently, even though ITU-T K.113 suggest that the maximum speed should remain within the 5 m limit between samples (speed of 18 km/h), the EMF RATEL protocol was adopted in accordance with the statement given in Section 6.1 – that “*speed requires adaptation to the state of the road*” [65].

f: PERIODICAL STOP THE VEHICLE TO PERFORM ADDITIONAL MEASUREMENTS WITH HANDHELD DEVICE

The protocol stipulates that the vehicle should be stopped periodically (at least every hour), to obtain a valid sample as a reference value, to which the driving measurements can be compared to ensure their reliability [65]. The reason for this is that the movement does not allow driving measurements to be taken for the average time of six minutes, as recommended by ICNIRP [35], [36].

Therefore, a broadband handheld measuring device [66] is used, as a reference device with an E-field probe of a similar frequency range as the main device installed on vehicle [57].

g: WHEN DRIVE TEST IS COMPLETE, TAKE THE MEASUREMENTS RESULTS AND COMPARE THEM WITH NATIONALLY PRESCRIBED REFERENCE LEVELS

The measurement results are downloaded from the device, using the accompanying software [57], and compared with 11 V/m – the lowest reference level in Serbia [51].

Furthermore, the measurement results are later formatted into a KML file, as explained in subsection III-A.2, for upload to the EMF RATEL driving test database.

h: IF THE MEASUREMENT IS ABOVE THE REFERENCE LEVEL, INDICATE THE SPECIFIC POINT FOR FURTHER INVESTIGATION

In the event that the value of any measurement is above the prescribed 11 V/m, the measuring point is marked for future additional investigation using six minutes averaged measurements, as recommended by ICNIRP [35], [36].

Regarding the second adaptation, it should be noted that the ITU-T K.113 suggest that “all measurements taken in motion are at least 6 dB (50%) below the most restrictive limit of the entire frequency band being measured with the probe”.

However, the EMF RATEL protocol uses value of 11 V/m, because Serbian legislation has a specificity – it already uses 2.5 times lower reference levels of ICNIRP 1998 [67].

2) DETAILS ABOUT MEASURING EQUIPMENT

The main device is installed on the vehicle to measure the field strength and provide an overview of the RF-EMF levels in the entire area [57]. Its main characteristics are presented in Table 4, together with a handheld measuring device [66], which is used to measure the reference levels.

The devices are calibrated in accordance with the ISO/IEC 17025:2017 standard, in an accredited laboratory, where the calibration period is 24 months.

B. EMF RATEL DRIVE CAMPAIGNS

The first phase of EMF RATEL drive test planed six driving campaigns to establish functionality. However, many more will follow in near future, to demonstrate full potential of the drive test methodology.

1) CAMPAIGN DURATION

Some measurement details for each campaign are shown in Table 5, where it can be seen that the measurement duration ranges from one and a half hours to almost six hours.

This time period highlights the challenges in driving conditions and traffic in the largest cities of Serbia, with Belgrade as the capital being the largest, followed by Novi Sad and Nis.

Due to the size of these cities and especially the density of traffic on their roads, it was almost necessary for practical reasons to adopt the driving speed, as explained in subsection IV-A.1.e for the protocol. However, during these campaigns, the number of E-field measurement samples collected ranges from 1735 to 7776, along the planned driving routes.

2) CAMPAIGN COVERAGE

The driving campaigns are planned to cover the most populated parts of the cities. According to the “Measure distance” tool on Google maps [68], the official area of a given city and the area covered by the corresponding campaign are shown in Table 5, where it can be seen that the percentage of coverage ranges from 4.17% to 14.87%.

The coverage of the driving campaign is demonstrated in the case of the city of Novi Sad in Fig. 31, where the Google tool was used to surround the inner area of the route, as shown in the figure. However, the coverage percentage should only be taken as a rough indication of what was covered by the campaign implemented, not as an accurate measure of its quality.

In most cases the drive campaign must be planned to cover those parts of the city where the majority of the population lives or which are most visited by the public. According to

TABLE 5. Details of Drive Test Campaigns.

No.	City name	Campaign name	Campaign date	Campaign start	Campaign end	Duration	Number of samples	Urban city area [km ²]	Area of campaign [km ²]	Campaign area/ Urban city area [%]
1.	Belgrade	BG – November 2024	11/8/2024	9:02:08 AM	3:03:33 PM	6:01:25	7776	395.97	23.08	5.83
2.	Jagodina	JA – February 2025	2/20/2025	2:52:10 PM	4:17:50 PM	1:25:40	1735	17.95	2.67	14.87
3.	Kragujevac	KG – March 2025	3/27/2025	11:38:22 AM	2:23:27 PM	2:45:05	3455	82.43	3.73	4.53
4.	Nis	NI – February 2025	2/20/2025	9:27:18 AM	12:31:38 PM	3:04:20	4201	42.71	5.95	13.93
5.	Novi Sad	NS – November 2024	11/14/2024	12:04:29 PM	3:52:43 PM	3:48:14	3821	80.44	6.48	8.06
6.	Subotica	SU – April 2025	4/2/2025	11:42:18 AM	2:16:36 PM	2:34:18	4132	166.37	6.93	4.17

FIGURE 31. Campaign coverage in the city of Novi Sad.

this indicator, most sources of RF-EMF are located in such a way as to cover that area and ensure good quality of existing telecommunication services, consequently radiating most of the RF-EMF in those areas.

C. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF DRIVE MEASUREMENT

The initial phase of EMF RATEL drive test was completed with 25120 measurement results collected.

Given the large number of results obtained, two types of statistical analysis were used. The first, the so-called five-number summary of the dataset, uses the minimum, Q1, median, Q3 and maximum to provide a quick insight into the distribution of the dataset [52], while the second uses density estimation to obtain the probability of occurrence of the results [69].

1) FIVE-NUMBER SUMMARY

The five-number summary is shown in Fig. 32.

It can be observed that the mean values for all campaigns are relatively similar, with a slightly increased value in the city of Belgrade compared to other cities.

Furthermore, the range between quartiles Q1 and Q3 [52] per city suggests that there is a fairly similar use of telecommunication services among the population in the monitored cities, since, relative to the city population density, 50% of the measured E-field levels are in a relatively similar range, defined by (Q3 – Q1).

Finally, regarding the Q3 level, which is the highest in the city of Belgrade and is slightly above 2 V/m, it can be noted that the majority of the collected E-field results (75% of them) are below 11 V/m, which is the lowest reference level

prescribed in Serbian legislation [51]. However, there are some field values in Belgrade (18.94 V/m), Nis (58.94 V/m) and Subotica (27.38 V/m) that indicate the need for further discussion and comprehensive research to confirm why such increased values are present in certain locations in these cities.

Additional numerical details of the statistical analysis from Fig. 32 can be seen in Table 6.

2) DENSITY ESTIMATION

A more comprehensive analysis of the collected field results by campaign can be obtained by use of kernel density estimation (*kde*) [69], as shown in Fig. 33.

It can be observed that for five out of six drive campaigns, only one density peak is present, which is below the value of 1.5 V/m, as the E-field value for which the Q3 quartiles are in four out of six campaigns below. This fact suggests that for most campaigns the E-field values are relatively low and well below the prescribed 11 V/m [51].

The *kde* distribution for the city of Belgrade is wider than for other cities, which indicates the diversity of E-field levels across the urban area, caused by population density and availability of telecommunication services, and as a consequence has a significant use of those wireless telecom services in the modern era.

This finding is consistent with the intensity of mobile phone signal coverage in the Republic of Serbia [70], provided by RATEL authority, and shown in Fig. 34, for the case of one national operator and its 4G service.

Figure 34 shows that Belgrade, as the largest city in Serbia, has the best 4G signal coverage, as well as 2G and 3G signals, of all operators [70], reflecting to current E-field levels.

A further overview of the collected results can be obtained by analyzing the cumulative distribution function (*cdf*) [69], shown in Fig. 35.

It can be observed that in the city of Belgrade there are lower probabilities when the E-field will be less than or equal to a certain value [69], compared to other cities, which once again indicates that there is a diversity of existing field levels in the Belgrade environment, which is related to obvious correlation: population density – use of telecommunication services [70].

D. DRIVE TEST AND CONTINUOUS RF-EMF MONITORING

Situations where monitoring sensors are located within the drive test area are present in several cities, allowing for the potential comparison of detected E-field levels using RF-EMF sensors and measurements from the drive test.

1) CASE STUDY OF THE CITY OF NOVI SAD

The EMF RATEL system has six installed RF-EMF sensors for continuous E-field monitoring in the city of Novi Sad, and the locations of five of them are shown in Fig. 36 (A, B, C, D and E), along with the conducted drive test campaign [29].

In this case study, the drive campaign was closest to sensor marked with D, installed at the kindergarten “NS – PU

TABLE 6. Statistical analysis by campaign.

City	Min	Mean	Max	St.dev.	Median	Q1	Q3
	[V/m]						
Belgrade	0.00	1.56	18.94	1.14	1.34	0.82	2.08
Jagodina	0.00	1.09	3.88	0.61	0.97	0.64	1.44
Kragujevac	0.00	1.00	5.88	0.73	0.88	0.39	1.43
Nis	0.00	0.86	58.94	2.04	0.59	0.33	0.97
Novi Sad	0.00	1.15	4.14	0.75	0.97	0.56	1.62
Subotica	0.00	0.87	27.38	0.87	0.75	0.46	1.10

TABLE 7. Comparison of rf-emf sensor and driving test.

RF-EMF sensor D	Drive test
11/14/2024 13:12:00 – 3.18 V/m	11/14/2024 13:14:53 – 2.42 V/m
	11/14/2024 13:14:55 – 2.70 V/m
11/14/2024 13:18:00 – 3.20 V/m	11/14/2024 13:14:57 – 2.64 V/m

Radosno detinjstvo, Veseli vrtić” [71], with a distance of 32 m, in horizontal plane (measured by Google), as shown in Fig. 37.

The E-field values from the sensor and the drive test that are closest in time are shown in Table 7.

These values are very similar, not even exact. However, it should be noted that the sensor was installed on the roof of the kindergarten building (almost 5 m above the ground), while the drive measurements were made on the road, near the building, on the roof of a vehicle (2 m above the ground). Therefore, given these heights, it cannot be expected that the field values will be the same.

Nevertheless, this small example demonstrates the possibilities of comparison between two different methodologies for E-field observing; however, the full power of the observation comes from the possibility of analyzing the behavior of the E-field at the monitoring location throughout the day, as shown in Fig. 38, as well as for any other days or even more, some long-term period, as shown in Fig. 7.

2) SYSTEMATIC OVERVIEW OF SENSOR AND DRIVE ROUTE DISTANCES

As for other cities in Serbia, a brief overview of the distance between the sensor and the drive route is given in Table 8, where sensors with distances less than 50 m are analyzed. Any greater distance may question the reliability of the comparison of results.

In some cases, the obtained field levels are comparable, as is the case with the sensors “KG – City Administration Kragujevac” in the city of Kragujevac and “NS – PU Radosno detinjstvo, Veseli vrtić” in Novi Sad. However, in some other cases there is a large difference between the values, as a result of the different position and height of the measuring devices, as well as the different concept of their use – observation by drive test analyzes the spatial distribution of the E-fields, using moving vehicle, helping the population to obtain information about the field levels, almost in every corner of their microenvironment, and not only about the fixed location of the RF-EMF sensor.

TABLE 8. Overview of the distances between sensors and the drive path in cities (distance less than 50 m).

No.	City	Location name	Distance	RF-EMF sensor	Drive test	E- field activity
1.	Belgrade	BG - OS "Milan Rakic"	46 m	11/08/2024 11:39:00 – 2.83 V/m	11/08/2024 11:29:01 – 0.82 V/m 11/08/2024 11:29:03 – 0.79 V/m 11/08/2024 11:29:05 – 0.46 V/m	Peak
2.		BG - Studentski dom "Zarko Marinovic"	46 m	11/08/2024 10:48:00 – 2.41 V/m 11/08/2024 10:54:00 – 2.37 V/m	11/08/2024 10:51:47 – 1.26 V/m 11/08/2024 10:51:48 – 1.15 V/m 11/08/2024 10:51:50 – 1.40 V/m	Typical
3.	Kragujevac	KG - Fakultet inzenjerskih nauka	30 m	27/03/2025 14:24:00 – 4.18 V/m	03/27/2025 14:23:22 – 1.38 V/m 03/27/2025 14:23:24 – 1.55 V/m 03/27/2025 14:23:27 – 1.77 V/m	Typical
4.		KG - Gradska uprava Kragujevac	38 m	03/27/2025 12:30:00 – 2.09 V/m 03/27/2025 12:36:00 – 1.89 V/m	03/27/2025 12:31:08 – 2.39 V/m 03/27/2025 12:31:10 – 2.57 V/m 03/27/2025 12:31:12 – 2.49 V/m	Peak
5.	Nis	NI - Vrtic "Bajka"	11 m	02/20/2025 09:48:00 – 0.72 V/m	02/20/2025 09:48:32 – 0.34 V/m 02/20/2025 09:48:35 – 0.12 V/m 02/20/2025 09:48:37 – 0.23 V/m	Typical
6.		NI - Vrtic "Crvenkapa"	40 m	02/20/2025 12:12:00 – 1.99 V/m 02/20/2025 12:18:00 – 1.97 V/m	02/20/2025 12:15:12 – 0.51 V/m 02/20/2025 12:15:14 – 0.38 V/m 02/20/2025 12:15:16 – 0.51 V/m	Peak
7.	Novi Sad	NS - PU Radosno detinjstvo, Veseli vrtic	32 m	11/14/2024 13:12:00 – 3.18 V/m 11/14/2024 13:18:00 – 3.20 V/m	11/14/2024 13:14:53 – 2.42 V/m 11/14/2024 13:14:55 – 2.70 V/m 11/14/2024 13:14:57 – 2.64 V/m	Peak

TABLE 9. Overview of the number of samples by specific range of e-field values.

Campaigns	Number of samples								Total	
	0-0.1 V/m	0.1-0.5 V/m	0.5-1 V/m	1-2 V/m	2-6 V/m	6-11 V/m	11-18 V/m	18-24 V/m		>24 V/m
Belgrade	33	820	1858	2952	2078	22	12	1	0	7776
Jagodina	10	272	633	683	137	0	0	0	0	1735
Kragujevac	131	927	892	1163	342	0	0	0	0	3455
Nis	170	1628	1408	801	170	7	10	1	6	4201
Novi Sad	33	812	1135	1260	581	0	0	0	0	3821
Subotica	35	1177	1651	1116	148	2	0	0	3	4132

However, a suitable combination of these two methodologies can be useful for expanding the knowledge on existing E-fields, as well as for analyzing their presence in the environment from different perspectives. For example, sensor data, as shown in Fig. 38, can be used to determine whether a measurement during a drive test occurred during a period of typical, peak or low field activity for that location, which can be useful for planning a future campaign on the same route. This feature can be seen as a strong demonstration of the integrated analytical capabilities of the system. Therefore, both of these methodologies should be further developed and efforts should be made to combine them, as was done in the EMF RATEL monitoring system and shown in Fig 36 [29].

Such a combination and the public availability of their measurements can help the general public to obtain the necessary information to establish a rational perception of the inevitable presence of E-field in the environment, relying on valid field observation.

V. RESULTS DISCUSSION

The initial goal of this paper was to present the technical details of the integration of the drive test into the Serbian EMF RATEL system. However, some very interesting results were observed and this section will elaborate them in more detail.

A. ANALYSIS OF HIGH-FIELD MEASUREMENTS

The drive test measurements have observed several high E-field values, as reported in subsection IV-C.1: in Belgrade – 18.94 V/m, Nis – 58.94 V/m and Subotica – 27.38 V/m, which exceed the national reference level of 11 V/m [51].

Regarding the EMF RATEL drive test protocol, discussed in IV.A.1, the locations with these high field values have been marked for future comprehensive analysis. However, some preliminary conclusions can be drawn, as will be presented in the following subsections.

1) NUMBER OF POINTS WITH FIELD VALUES ABOVE THE THRESHOLD

By analyzing individual drive measurements, an overview of the sample data can be obtained, as shown in Table 9.

It can be seen that for Belgrade $(12 + 1) = 13$ measurements exceed the prescribed level of 11 V/m, which is only 0.17% of the total results (7776 measurements). Moreover, for Nis $(10 + 1 + 6) = 17$ samples are above the prescribed limit, which is 0.4% (of 4201), while for the city of Subotica 3 measurements are above 11 V/m, which is 0.07% of total results (4132).

Even these percentages can be considered almost negligible, increased E-field values can cause enormous concern to

FIGURE 32. Five-number summary by drive test campaigns.

FIGURE 33. kde distribution by campaign.

the general public and therefore deserve special attention and all possible RF-EMF research.

2) HIGH FIELD SPOTS AND ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS

A relatively easy investigation can be a preliminary analysis of the environment near spots with increased field intensity, as shown in Fig. 39, for the case of the city of Nis.

Both positions, P1 and P2, with these field levels are located in less populated parts of the city, while it can be noted that their drive measurement locations in both cases are located at an intersection with an electrified railway line, as shown in Fig. 40. The measurement details in these spots are shown in Table 10.

The third interesting location in the city is outside of the populated area, near the city cemetery and nearby power lines, as shown in Fig. 41, where 9 detected field levels are in the range of 11-18 V/m, with details shown in Table 11.

In this situation, the drive test vehicle passed closed to high-voltage power lines, similar to the cases of locations P1 and P2, which most likely caused unwanted electromagnetic

FIGURE 34. RATEL coverage map [70].

FIGURE 35. cdf distribution by campaign.

induction in the main measuring device, as well as consequently increased field values.

Moreover, in this particular case, an effect of approaching/removing from the power line can be observed, where the E-field levels gradually increase/decrease. Moreover, looking at locations P1 and P2, the E-field levels at the locations close to the railway suddenly become low and remain so, further supporting the possibility that induction is the main cause of the increased field levels.

These three situations (P1-P3) are present also in the cases of the cities of Belgrade and Subotica, where similar increased field levels were detected [29]. It is preliminary possible that induction is the reason for the increased field

FIGURE 36. Driving test campaign in Novi Sad and locations of RF-EMF sensors for continuous monitoring.

FIGURE 37. The distance between the sensor and the drive route.

FIGURE 38. Field behavior at location “Veseli vrtić” for 11/14/2024 [71].

levels along the considered driving routes. However, this cannot be a general conclusion and further comprehensive RF-EMF investigations must be carried out at these locations.

B. EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT

Section III-A.4 presents the details of the exposure assessment procedure in the EMF RATEL drive test, which is based

on the estimation of exposure boundaries, as the most appropriate approach for cases with broadband measurements [61].

Regarding the frequency range of $f_{min} = 100$ kHz to $f_{max} = 8$ GHz for the field probe of the main measuring device [57], the following minimum and maximum prescribed levels are used for the assessment/calculation of the boundaries: $E_{refmin} = 11$ V/m and $E_{refmax} = 34.8$ V/m [51], shown in Fig. 20

However, such an assessment process is performed under the assumption that RF-EMF radiation is constantly present at all frequencies in the range 100 kHz to 8 GHz, which in many cases may not be true, given the variations in real-life spectral content at different locations, along the driving test route.

In case only part of the frequency range is occupied, with f_{minnew} and f_{maxnew} , this will be reflected in the values $E_{refminnew}$ and $E_{refmaxnew}$, and will result in new exposure boundaries, so-called adaptive [61], as shown in Fig. 42.

The result of the adaptive approach is that the estimate of the range in which the actual exposure falls will be more precise, as already discussed in [61]. This fact suggests that the accuracy of these boundaries depends to a large extent on the spectral content at the measurement point, as well as on the frequency of the dominant RF-EMF source [61].

Unfortunately, given the nature and realization of the drive test, it is almost impossible to analyze spectral content at each point in order to accurately estimate the boundaries.

On the other hand, considering the potentially worst-case of exposure, the old boundaries are also quite acceptable and

FIGURE 39. High field intensity locations in the city of Nis.

FIGURE 40. Two of three high field locations in the city of Nis [29].

TABLE 10. Details of P1 and P2 measurements.

P1	02/20/2025 09:53:07 – 57.05 V/m	P2	02/20/2025 09:54:33 – 51.56 V/m
	02/20/2025 09:53:12 – 19.82 V/m		02/20/2025 09:54:36 – 30.07 V/m
			02/20/2025 10:00:59 – 31.48 V/m
			02/20/2025 10:01:04 – 48.59 V/m
			02/20/2025 10:06:01 – 58.94 V/m
			02/20/2025 10:06:04 – 16.56 V/m

FIGURE 41. Third high field location in the city of Nis [29].

FIGURE 42. Adaptive exposure boundaries [61].

TABLE 11. Drive test measurements near power lines.

P3	
02/20/2025	11:38:14 – 11.86 V/m
02/20/2025	11:38:16 – 15.41 V/m
02/20/2025	11:38:18 – 16.18 V/m
02/20/2025	11:38:21 – 16.22 V/m
02/20/2025	11:38:29 – 15.97 V/m
02/20/2025	11:38:35 – 15.34 V/m
02/20/2025	11:38:41 – 14.41 V/m
02/20/2025	11:38:48 – 13.94 V/m
02/20/2025	11:38:52 – 12.56 V/m

this is the main reason why the exposure boundaries and the entire frequency range $f_{min} = 100$ kHz to $f_{max} = 8$ GHz, of the E-field probe, is used for the exposure assessment in the EMF RATEL drive test.

C. THE SPEED OF DRIVING VEHICLE

The EMF RATEL drive test protocol, discussed in IV.A.1 subsection, is established on the ITU-T K.113 recommendations [65]; however, it does not strictly follow all its provisions, since they are not mandatory.

Accordingly, two specific adaptations have been made for EMF RATEL, one of which is the speed of the driving vehicle.

Practical reasons have imposed an adjustment of the driving speed, even setting it from 18 km/h (recommended by

ITU-T K.113 for urban environments and a measurement time of 1 s) to 36 km/h, or even more, can affect the spacing between measurement points, as well as the probability of detecting localized hot spots (if this is the primary intention of the driving test) and the accuracy of the reported maximum values.

However, numerous real-life situations with traffic density in Serbian cities, and in particular the issuance of a special permit for low-speed vehicles and the mandatory engagement of traffic police escort in such cases, stay behind decision that EMF RATEL protocol deviates slightly from the ITU-T K.113 recommendations [65]. The goal was to implement planned driving test campaigns as efficiently as possible, which would not be possible on a large scale, in terms of a larger number of campaigns, if the permit/traffic police escort were mandatory.

D. THE CAMPAIGN'S SET SIZE

Unfortunately, a set of only six drive campaigns, especially one per city is a relatively small set for any solid summary on the behavior of the E-field over analyzed routes.

This initial set can be seen as a limitation of the work done in this paper; however, it was primarily used to test the system functionality and as an example of potential analyses. There is a plan to conduct about a dozen more campaigns, in the last quarter of 2025, as well as in 2026, in order to establish a richer EMF system.

In addition to the new campaigns, the routes that were originally driven will also be monitored annually, in order to establish a comprehensive dataset of RF-EMF measurements for prospective comparative analyses of the spatial behavior of the field in a given area.

Therefore, in the future, an increase in the size of the campaign set should be expected, which will allow for more diverse and detailed analyses, followed by appropriate conclusions.

E. SYNERGY VALUE OF EMF RATEL

The goal of integrating the drive test functionality into EMF RATEL was to create, for the first time, a single EMF entity that is capable of offering observational measurement results of both temporal and spatial E-field changes.

Regarding the coexistence of these two types of fields examination, there may be a high level of complementarity where drive test can be used to identify near-optimal locations for new fixed sensors, by detecting increased spatial variation in a given area, in which the appropriate location can be used for temporal monitoring.

Moreover, monitoring the E-field using a sensor, together with an accompanying annual analysis of field fluctuations, can trigger a targeted drive campaign in its vicinity to further investigate the current effects of the E-field.

Furthermore, the strong complementarity of temporal and spatial approaches can produce additional value if correlation with known RF-EMF sources in the territory (e.g., cellular base stations, broadcast towers, etc.) can be established.

Unfortunately, the Republic of Serbia does not yet have a public and open register of E-field sources and therefore, at present, the EMF RATEL system cannot use information from such a register. However, in the future, it can be expected that this specific monitoring system or some other system will use a national register with technical parameters that allow more precise planning of temporal/spatial field monitoring.

In addition to the numerous, foreseen applications of the EMF RATEL capabilities, the expected implementation of 5G technology in the Republic of Serbia, may highlight the potential dual purpose of this valuable RF-EMF tool. One that not only informs the public about current exposure levels, which is valuable for the periods before and after the implementation of 5G, but can also provide some key data to network operators for analyzing the coverage, interference and performance of their mobile networks and services, which opens an additional application dimension of the EMF RATEL system, as well as some other monitoring systems. Therefore, this work encourages other, similar RF-EMF systems to make additional efforts and integrate drive test, in a similar or even improved way than it was done in EMF RATEL and therefore to further develop the topic of RF-EMF observation.

VI. CONCLUSION

The EMF research community is investing significant efforts in measuring/assessing human exposure, while innovating existing and creating some new appropriate methodologies, among which the drive test has attracted attention. However, a gap in research has been noted, where the results of the drive test are published in numerous scientific papers, while unfortunately they cannot be found integrated into any specific EMF entity and offered to the wider community.

The Serbian EMF RATEL system has been continuously monitoring RF-EMF in the environment since 2017. Unfortunately, its monitoring is based on a relatively small number of scattered locations, where it was possible to perform analyses of the behavior of the existing E-field over some long-term periods. In addition to these activities, in 2024, this monitoring system was enhanced by integrating the test drive functionality, for the first time among existing monitoring systems, with the aim of enabling an additional perspective of RF-EMF observation – spatial analysis over the desired area and routes of interest, especially within urban areas.

In order to upgrade the system, several technical steps are foreseen, and the focus of this paper is on presenting the integration process, explaining the necessary work on expanding and modifying the existing EMF RATEL information logistics, in order to combine field data from temporal and spatial measurements.

A detailed explanation is given on the modeling of the test drive database, data parsing, dissemination via the system's public web portal, as well as management activities in the

administrative aspect, regarding cities, associated test drive campaigns, their measurement results, etc.

In addition, several quantitative results of the conducted campaigns are presented, including the results of the analysis of the collected field levels and their statistical distribution, highlighting that the majority of the collected electric field levels are well below the minimum reference level of 11 V/m, prescribed by the Serbian EMF law.

However, during the driving tests, some increased E-field values were observed in the cities of Belgrade (18.94 V/m), Nis (58.94 V/m) and Subotica (27.38 V/m), which were analyzed and where electromagnetic induction was detected as a possible reason for the increased field levels along the considered driving routes. This is not a general conclusion and further comprehensive RF-EMF research needs to confirm why such field levels are present at specific locations.

Also, some of the results of a general review of continuous E-field monitoring by EMF RATEL are presented, together with a discussion of the potential benefits of combining observations via RF-EMF sensors and driving tests, for the analysis of the temporal and spatial behavior of the field.

By offering these results via a national open data framework, their combination can be useful in several ways, not only for the general public, but also for many stakeholders, from EMF laboratories, telecommunications operators, environmental protection agencies, EMF decision makers, the scientific community, to EMF standardization bodies.

The aim of this paper is also to promote the advantages of combining continuous field monitoring via RF-EMP sensors and spatial observation via drive tests and to encourage other, similar EMP monitoring systems to further develop the topic of RF-EMP observations, as was done in EMF RATEL.

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